

VISS

First report on capacity building resources and actions/D7.5

WP7, T7.5

Month 25 (September), Year 2025

Authors: Maite Ferrando (KVELOCE); Aran Blanco (KVELOCE); José Benedicto (KVELOCE), Marcello Bardellini (ICONS)

Identification (File name): D7.5. First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

Co-Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, REA or UKRI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Grant No. 101081931

Technical references

Project Acronym	ViSS
Project Title	Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications
Project Coordinator	Jose Antonio Plaza Hernández CETEC coordination@viss-project.org
Project Duration	September 2023 – August 2027 (48 months)
Deliverable No.	D7.5
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP7 - ViSS outreach: Communication, dissemination, exploitation and capacity building
Task	T7.5 – Open Innovation and Capacity Building
Lead beneficiary	13- KVELOCE
Contributing beneficiary/ies	1-CETEC; 3-VTT; 4- IRIS; 5-HELIAN; 6-IDENER; 7-UA; 9-AITEX; 11 ZUKAN; 12-TCA, 14-ICONS; 15-BHAM,
Due date of deliverable	28 February 2025
Submission date v1.0	28 February 2025
Submission date v2.0	15 September 2025

* PU = Public- Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page).

SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

Document History

v	Date	Beneficiary	
v0.1	07/02/2025	KVC	First draft of document
v0.2	14/02/2025	AITEX	Revised version based on the comments of Pablo Lopez, AITEX
v1.0	20/02/2024	KVC	First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, submitted to EC.
V2.0	02/09/2025	KVC	Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, resubmitted to EC. The document now incorporates the previously missing reference to Table 1 in section 4.1 (page 8).

Verification and approval v1.0

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Marcello Bardellini	27/02/2025
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Isabel Sánchez	27/02/2025

Verification and approval v2.0

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Chiara Locuratolo	09/09/2025
Approval Final Deliverable by Coordinator	Carmen Fernández Ayuso	15/09/2025

Table of contents

1. List of abbreviations	5
2. Objectives and scope.....	5
3. Introduction: ViSS Open Innovation processes.....	6
4. Undertaken activities and Action Plan.....	8
4.1 Review, partner responsibilities, and stakeholder engagement.....	8
4.2 Resources.....	9
4.3 Undertaken activities	10
4.3.1 Seminar on ViSS SSbD to the Joint Research Centre at Ispra (Italy)	10
4.3.2 Seminar on ViSS SSbD to the Joint Research Centre in Brussels (Belgium).....	11
4.1 Upcoming activities	12
5. Dissemination and Communication.....	13
6. Conclusions	14
7. References	15

List of Tables

Table 1: Capacity building activities.....	9
--	---

List of Figures

Figure 1: Open Innovation processes	7
Figure 2: Example slides of slideshow for capacity building.....	10
Figure 3: JRC centre in Ispra	11
Figure 4: Frontpage of slideshow at Ispra.....	11
Figure 5: Screen during KVELOCE presentation	12
Figure 6: Maite Ferrando (KVELOCE) during the presentation at JRC in Belgium	12
Figure 7: Calendarization of Capacity Building activities	12
Figure 8: Detailed calendar of Capacity Building activities.....	13

1. List of abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
Dn.n	Deliverable number
DoA	Description of Action
JRC	Joint Research Centre
Mn	Month of the project
OI	Open Innovation
R+D	Research and Development
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
Tn.n	Task number
CEBM	Circular Economy Business Models

2. Objectives and scope

This document constitutes the deliverable D7.5 First report on capacity building resources and actions and is a summary of activities that have been performed by the ViSS project within Task 7.5 Open Innovation and capacity building, from Month 9 to Month 18. This activity falls under ViSS WP7: **ViSS Outreach – Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Capacity Building**. As such, the Capacity Building activities serve to complement both the **ViSS Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy (T7.1)** and the **Public Engagement Strategy (T7.3)**.

The **objective of the open innovation and capacity building in ViSS** is:

- to **elaborate on the lessons learnt during several research activities and consultations of the project**,
- to **deliver recommendations** aimed at:
 - enhancing the social readiness of bio-based plastics,
 - improving the communication of end-of-life routes of biodegradable packaging to consumers and industrial actors,
 - implementing standardisation and regulations processes,
 - promoting digital tools supporting SSbD & social readiness related assessment and
 - unveiling financing mechanisms and CE business models.

This report will be updated on M33 (D7.10 Interim report on capacity building resources; May 2026) with the activities implemented between Months 18 and 33 of the project, and on M48 (D7.16 Final capacity building resources and actions; August 2027) with the activities performed from M33 to M48 of the project. The lessons learnt during the capacity building activities will nurture other activities such as T7.3 (Public Engagement) and T7.4 (Networking and Clustering), being the basis for the delivery of recommendations to foster circular economy.

First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

On the other hand, the open innovation activities in T7.5 also encompass knowledge sharing actions with KCB Centre for Bioeconomy and JRC (Joint Research Centre), promoted through the project channels in T7.3 and T7.4.

3. Introduction: ViSS Open Innovation processes

Open Innovation (OI) is a concept introduced by Chesbrough in *Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology* (Chesbrough, 2003) that has raised its importance in both academic research, industrial practice and the public policy domain. The concept, in contrast with Close Innovation (CI) assumes that a single organisation cannot innovate in isolation and that the use of external ideas and internal ideas should be combined into platforms, architectures and systems to create value. It is important to highlight that “openness” in innovation is not a binary classification of open versus closed (Chesbrough, 2003; Dahlander and Gann, 2010) but rather a continuum of information flow processes covering varying degrees of openness, across organisational and sectoral borders using monetary or non-monetary incentives (Bogers et al., 2018) depending on the innovation processes that are implemented, each one involving advantages and disadvantages.

In VISS project, the R+D model is based on the **Quintuple Helix of Innovation** (Carayannis et al., 2012), as defined in D7.2 Public Engagement Strategy. Assuming the existence of a knowledge-based society, knowledge is considered the ‘most fundamental resource’ created through creative processes, combinations, and productions in so-called ‘Knowledge models’ or ‘Innovation models’ and thus becomes available for society. Beyond traditional “linear models of innovation”, in which academia and universities play a lead role in knowledge creation, the Quintuple Helix of Innovation is based on the coexistence and coevolution of different knowledge and innovation modes, encouraging interdisciplinary thinking and its transdisciplinary application, adding the industry and private sector, public administrations, civil society, as well as the environment understood as the interactions between society and nature as a (social) driver for innovation, creating incentives for more knowledge and better innovations.

OI relies on two important knowledge flows (Figure 1): Outside-In and Inside-Out, also referred as inbound and outbound OI. **Outside-in**, or inbound OI, is the part that has been more widely studied and applied, involving opening up the innovation processes in an organisation or project to many kinds of external inputs and contributions. Inside-out open innovation represents the opposite knowledge flow, which is not so widely known or applied, in which an organisation allows ideas to be applied by other companies or projects. On its part, **coupled OI** involve a more interactive mode of knowledge flowing into and out of the organization involving collaborative effort with innovation partners (Stanko et al., 2017).

Figure 1: Open Innovation processes

In the context of the European Union, the concept of Open Innovation 2.0 has been developed, moving from bilateral transactions and collaborations towards networked, multi-collaborative innovation ecosystems (Independent Expert Group Report on Open Innovation and Knowledge Transfer, 2014), assuming that innovation has impacts in the economic and social environment, such as customer’s behaviours, or development of sustainability policies. Hence, Open Innovation has a co-creation approach referring to the joint development of knowledge through relationships within consortia, that can encompass competitors, suppliers, customers as well as universities and public research organisations.

ViSS Open Innovation model encompasses the three types along its implementation:

- Inbound OI mechanisms are reflected in the Public Engagement strategy (D7.2). Particularly, at the Consult level, it is expected to gather feedback from project partners, industry (entrepreneurs and companies) and civil society, on their perception on the effectivity of ViSS solutions, the importance of environmental impacts in their practices, as well as their consumption and disposal habits of plastic packages;
- Outbound OI: these strategies are described with further detail along the different versions of the Data Management Plan (D8.2 Preliminary Data Management Plan; D8.4 Interim Data Management Plan; D8.5 Final Data Management Plan) and IPR strategy defined in Task 7.6. Moreover, capacity building activities reflected in this deliverable, such as seminars or webinars can be considered as outbound OI. Outbound OI collides with the concept of the “Openness paradox”, related with the tension between sharing and protecting that may impair the ability to effectively leverage external knowledge and develop innovation and therefore, it requires an effective management by tailoring specific strategies depending of the specific nature of knowledge (Bogers et al., 2018; Xie et al., 2025). Capacity building

First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

activities, understood in ViSS as those aimed at capacity acquisition, are needed to facilitate the inflow and outflow of knowledge and accelerate innovation, stimulating new ideas and to expand market opportunities for the external use of innovation (Cheng et al., 2016; Chesbrough, 2003; Robertson et al., 2023).

- Coupled OI: under this category, we could encompass the mechanisms included in the Public Engagement strategy (D7.2) specifically at the collaboration level, during the co-creation of the SSbD framework, as well as the Networking and Clustering activities framed in T7.4, in which EU and international markets and players will be mobilised and cooperation with relevant projects and initiatives is foreseen.

4. Undertaken activities and Action Plan

According to the concept of Open Innovation and the scope of the activity within the ViSS project (covering from M9, May 2024, to M48, August 2027), most of the Open Innovation and Capacity building activities have still not been implemented at the date of publication of this deliverable. This is also related with the early development stage of most of the innovations foreseen in ViSS.

Nevertheless, mapping and planning activities have been carried out from M9 to M18 (February 2025), accompanied by the preparation of capacity building materials that will be adapted to different target sectors and innovation topic in a collaborative manner, with contributions from all partners.

4.1 Review, partner responsibilities, and stakeholder engagement

During M9-M11, KVELOCE made a revision of the different topics that will be covered in the Capacity Building activities and the distribution of responsibilities among the partners for each topic. According to the Description of Action, more than 40 capacity building activities are to be implemented during the project, adapted to the partners' expertise. The distribution of the capacity building activities, together with the target groups for each topic and the partner's participation, is shown in Table 1. At least 5 webinars or seminars will be implemented for each topic.

Subsequently, and in collaboration with task T7.3, a database of stakeholders is being elaborated by the partners leading WP7 tasks (KVELOCE, ICONS, TCA) to define the specific actors that may be interested in participating in the Capacity Building activities.

First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

Table 1: Capacity building activities

Topics	Target	Responsible
policy recommendations on social readiness of consumers	policy makers & administrations	KVELOCE, IDE & UA
policy recommendations on standardisation	policy makers & administration packaging industry	TCA
policy and industrial recommendations related to further developments and end-of life scenarios, including sorting techniques/strategies	policy makers & administration	IRIS
	packaging industry	
replication study covering other industrial potential residues and applications	research community policy makers & administration food and packaging industry	TCA
SSbD and social readiness evaluation framework	research community food and packaging industry civil society organisations	KVELOCE+ IDE
digital tools supporting SSbD & social readiness	policy makers & administration food and packaging industry civil society organisations	KVELOCE+ CETEC
ViSS CEBM and its financing mechanisms	food and packaging industry	KVELOCE +ICONS
industry recommendations for safe and sustainable bio-based bioplastics	food and packaging industry	CETEC, BHAM, VTT, HP

4.2 Resources

During the first months of T7.5, a slideshow for webinars (Figure 2) has been prepared by KVELOCE, based on the project template shared by ICONS.

The slideshow remains available to the project partners participating in the task, since it will require tailoring contents to the different topics and stakeholders addressed by the Capacity Building Activities.

First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

Figure 2: Example slides of slideshow for capacity building

4.3 Undertaken activities

Some capacity building activities have been undertaken in the first 9 months of Task 7.5 Open Innovation and Capacity Building activities. On this regard, it should be taken into account that **most of the project’s results are in an early stage of development, and most of the activities planned will take place during the last year, when recommendations based on the lessons learnt can be extracted.**

4.3.1 Seminar on ViSS SSbD to the Joint Research Centre at Ispra (Italy)

On 12th June 2024, the SSbD framework developed in ViSS was presented to the JRC in Ispra (Figure 3) as a case study for implementation, framed within the *D3 Seminar: The SSbD framework into practice: a case study* (Figure 4). The target group attending the event were **12 civil servants**, interested in the concepts and assessment method described and the indicators selected in the ViSS projects. During the seminar, the participants had the opportunity **to engage discussions on the real case, exchanging knowledge on the methodology for indicators selection in the different SSbD dimensions, the development of scoring systems and the challenges on the harmonization.**

First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

Figure 3: JRC centre in Ispra

Figure 4: Frontpage of slideshow at Ispra

4.3.2 Seminar on ViSS SSbD to the Joint Research Centre in Brussels (Belgium)

On 5th and 6th December 2024, the 5th Stakeholder workshop on "Safe and sustainable by design" took place in Brussels and online. Along the two days of the event, different case studies for the application of the SSbD framework were presented, and the challenges were broadly discussed with stakeholders representing different projects. KVELOCE presented the case of ViSS framed in the seminar "Feedback from stakeholders during the second testing period -Sustainability assessment" (Figure 5, Figure 6).

Among the take aways of the seminar, **It was emphasized that the social and economic dimensions of SSbD are often overlooked, with a predominant focus on safety and environmental aspects, while a comprehensive sustainability vision remains lacking.** In addition, methods are still not harmonised between the different dimensions and there is a need of consensus-based methods.

The target group attending the event was approximately **80 civil servants**.

First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

Figure 5: Screen during KVELOCE presentation

Figure 6: Maite Ferrando (KVELOCE) during the presentation at JRC in Belgium

4.4 Upcoming activities

As shown in Figure 7, the capacity building actions will be performed from the second quartile of 2025 to the second quartile of 2027. **Figure 7: Calendarization of Capacity Building activities**

	Year 2			Year 3				Year 4			
	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026	Q2 2026	Q3 2026	Q4 2026	Q1 2027	Q2 2027	Q3 2027
Capacity building actions											

Figure 7: Calendarization of Capacity Building activities

The first activity will consist in holding internal meetings, identifying specific stakeholders that may be targeted by each of the topics of the capacity building activities planned (Table 1). Based on that classification, dissemination and communication resources and activities will be designed and implemented to maximize the outreach, in cooperation with Task 7.2 (Figure 8: Detailed calendar of Capacity Building activities)

First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

Subsequently, further slideshows and capacity building materials will be elaborated, based on the developments of the different technical WPs. These materials will be included in D7.10 (M33, May 2026) and D7.16 (M48, August 2027), including the adaptations required for each topic and the lessons learnt along the project implementation, such as the recommendations for different types of stakeholders.

Figure 8: Detailed calendar of Capacity Building activities

5. Dissemination and Communication

Dissemination and Communication activities are further detailed in D7.1 (Preliminary Plan of Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation), updated on M18 (February 2025) in the First report on Dissemination and Communication (D7.3). **Further adaptations, to reflect campaigns and materials specifically designed to promote Open Innovation and capacity building activities, will be included in the Interim Plan of Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation D7.8(M24, August 2025).**

During the time since the beginning of the project (September 2023) and the publication of this document (February 2025), the project has been disseminated through the main website and social media. Furthermore, **dissemination and communication materials with a stronger focus on capacity building will be designed in English** (for EU capacity building actions) **and Spanish**, for those carried out in Alicante and Murcia.

These materials will include brochures and flyers tailored for different actors. Special attention will be paid to multiplier agents such as cultural centres, business and innovation centres, universities holding degrees or masters on ViSS topics, commerce chambers, industrial clusters, etc.

The **most important objective** (primary objective) is to **enhance the acceptability of ViSS results**, which implies **to adopt the required technological and social innovations developed** in the project. ViSS campaigns aiming at open innovation and capacity building will be actively promoted through the media and official channels mentioned in D7.1 and the forthcoming update in D7.8 (platforms,

First report on capacity building resources and actions. v2.0

online social media, mass media, interpersonal channels, small group meetings, etc). The media of choice will depend on the key message and specific audiences for each communication campaign.

6. Conclusions

The objectives of Open Innovation and Capacity building in ViSS are to enhance the acceptability of ViSS results and solutions, through a range of materials and actions (e.g. workshops, roundtables, technical seminars), providing recommendations to:

- **enhance the social readiness of bio-based plastics** and how to properly communicate the end-of-life routes of biodegradable packaging to consumers
- **Raise awareness and build knowledge on missing aspects related to the standardisation and regulations processes** onto bio-based materials and products, as well as end-of life scenarios, including sorting techniques and strategies
- Foster the **replication of developments covering other industrial potential residues and applications.**
- **Promote the use and contribute with case studies on SSbD and social readiness**, as well as related tools such as digital platforms.
- **Raise awareness and build knowledge on ViSS Circular Economy Business Models (CEBM)** and related financing mechanisms.
- **Promote the adoption by industry of safe and sustainable bio-based bioplastics.**

The next steps will consist in:

- **Organising internal meetings with partners** to coordinate the elaboration of capacity building materials and activities, also connected with other activities as outlined in D7.4
- **Expanding the database of target groups potentially interested in coordination** with other tasks (T7.3 and T7.4).
- **Elaborating further slideshows and capacity building materials**, based on the developments of the different technical WPs, adapted for each of the topics to be offered
- Deliver dissemination materials with information on the different capacity building actions and design the channels and campaigns.

The results of the activity will be reported in following deliverables M33 (D7.10 Interim report on capacity building resources; May 2026) and on M48 (D7.16 Final capacity building resources and actions; August 2027).

7. References

Bogers, M., Chesbrough, H., & Moedas, C. (2018). Open innovation: Research, practices, and policies. *California Management Review*, 60(2), 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0008125617745086>

Carayannis, E. G., Barth, T. D., & Campbell, D. F. (2012). The quintuple helix innovation model: Global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2192-5372-1-2>

Cheng, C. C. J., Yang, C., & Sheu, C. (2016). Effects of open innovation and knowledge-based dynamic capabilities on radical innovation: An empirical study. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 41, 79–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jengtecman.2016.07.002>

Chesbrough, H. (2003). *Open innovation: The new imperative for creating and profiting from technology*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.

Dahlander, L., & Gann, D. M. (2010). How open is innovation? *Research Policy*, 39(6), 699–709. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2010.01.013>

European Commission, Independent Expert Group on Open Innovation and Knowledge Transfer. (2014). *Boosting open innovation and knowledge transfer in the European Union*. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/72620>

Robertson, J., Caruana, A., & Ferreira, C. (2023). Innovation performance: The effect of knowledge-based dynamic capabilities in cross-country innovation ecosystems. *International Business Review*, 32, 101866. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2021.101866>

Stanko, M. A., Fisher, G. J., & Bogers, M. (2017). Under the wide umbrella of open innovation. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 34(4), 543–558. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpim.12392>

Xie, C., Yang, N., Wang, Y., & Zhang, M. (2025). Firm's openness and innovation radicalness within R&D networks: Reconciling the openness paradox through the network pluralism view. *Technovation*, 141, 103163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2024.103163>